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UNITED STATES-CHINA RELATIONS IN THE PROCESS OF GLOBAL CHANGE

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Annotation. *This article covers the state of global processes change on a global scale, domination on the ground of these changes, fundamental turns in economic and international relations, conflicts in US-China trade relations, its causes and consequences, the competition of two states and their impact on the global economy, and the strategies of the United States and China in global governance.*

Keywords: *global processes, economy, global governance, international relations, investment, strategies, conflicts.*

ОТНОШЕНИЯ США И КИТАЯ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ГЛОБАЛЬНЫХ ИЗМЕНЕНИЙ

Аннотация. *В данной статье освещается состояние изменений глобальных процессов в мировом масштабе, господство на земле этих изменений, коренные повороты в экономических и международных отношениях, напряженность в американо-китайских торговых отношениях, ее причины и последствия, конкуренция двух стран и влияние на мировую экономику, стратегии США и Китая в глобальном управлении.*

Ключевые слова: *глобальные процессы, экономика, глобальное управление, электроника, международные отношения, инвестиции, производство, пандемия, конвергентный интерес, кризис, искусственный интеллект.*

As we all know, global processes are undergoing changes on a global scale. In governance and politics, there are shifts from monoculture to polyculture. We can witness the fundamental turns in domination, economic and international relations on the ground of these changes.

The hegemonic states that play a key role in such a political arena can be a clear witness in the relations of the United States and China in particular.

Experts believe that the softening of the conflict in US-China trade relations is expected to slow down the provision of continuity in the global process. But this situation determines the direction of huge investments in recent years.

According to analysts, as of 2018, there has been a rejection of trade tariffs imposed on most of China's manufactured goods as well as its products. This situation leads to the development of the economy, the emergence of continuity of supply of raw materials and spare parts for significant goods in the field of electronics. But the focus of World investment on China is disappointing Asian countries such as Indonesia, the Philippines, Thailand, Vietnam. The reason was that the US-China conflict was being used by the economies of these countries.

To get rid of trade tariffs, a certain number of companies that had withdrawn their manufacturing industries from the Chinese state had been moved to Taiwan. In particular, the placement of electronics and chip manufacturing enterprises, considered a valuable industry, was a significant contribution to the improvement of Taiwan's economic situation. Currently, Taiwan has developed into a world electronics and chip manufacturing center.

We all know from history that by the middle of the 20th century, the world powers were very indifferent to the future of China, and China was practically not considered a global power. Supposedly, it was considered a large and poor country. At that time, the economy of China had an annual gross domestic product of less than \$ 60 per capita. The American scientist Carnegie later develops a report called China, which he quotes in the report that what we see is a rapidly changing China that gives us optimism and anxiety. Since his report, China has begun to rise to unprecedented heights in the world's production lines, increasing its economy and power. Its economy grew almost twenty times, making it the second largest economy in the world after the United States.

At present, China has managed to become one of the global leaders in manufacturing, technology and science. Its global impact grew, reaching from Asia and Africa to the Middle East and Latin America

These circumstances can become a serious problem for American statehood in decades. The United States and China have entered competition in all sectors of global

governance in a significant way during this period. At the same time, the rivalry of the two states does not lose the likelihood of convergent interests for different purposes.

Indeed, these countries can cooperate on other issues of the world's development, which are becoming more relevant today: in the world experiencing the current climate crisis, it should be aimed at preparing requirements for the management of artificial intelligence, silencing nuclear problems, preventing the next secular pandemic.

The states of the United States and China have obligations to prevent the World War, their citizens and the countries of the world.

In recent times, the way in which both countries conduct and manage their relations has a significant impact on World Development. "How can China and America live peacefully?", depending on the turbulent situation in the time we live, at the same time they will have to imagine the results of the destruction of hope for a peaceful and stable future. In this regard, the necessary measure provides for the implementation of measures.

Disputes in the South China Sea

Description

— China ... Philippines ... Malaysia ... Brunei Darussalam ... Vietnam

Oil and Gas:

Oil and gas are not yet exploited. Deposits are believed under the sea floor

Trade:

Trade with ships the South China Sea is worth more of 5 trillion US dollars annually

Figure 1. U.S. support for the Philippines on the South China Sea issue

U.S. support for the Philippines on the South China Sea issue would in turn lead to increased tensions in its relations with China as well as its support for Taiwan. This, in turn, will be able to lead to the emergence of problems in the global economy, in particular in the field of transport and logistics. The tension and uncertainty that is significantly observed, in turn, will create an obstacle to the development of international relations.

Currently, the national interests of the United States and China are different in the current period of preventing nuclear war and pursuing policies in the interests of nations That is why we are required to be able to identify these differences and be in an elegant position.

To create a constructive and promising future for US-China relations in the future, we will use reality-based practical resources.

In place of the conclusion, it can be said that the strengthening of cooperation, which is relevant for the prospect of the US and China World Order, makes it possible to think that the geopolitical competition between the two states of a common destiny often makes it impossible to exchange mutually beneficial economic exchange in the future. While each of them will continue to try to maximize their alliances and strength, it will lead to a huge crisis for the world

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